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MODELING DETERMINANTS OF STUDENT KNOWLEDGE ON GUT MICROBIOTA: A NEGATIVE BINOMIAL REGRESSION APPROACH

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Introduction: Understanding probiotics and gut microbiota is essential for healthcare professionals. This study aimed to mathematically model predictors of medical students' knowledge using a negative binomial regression (NBR) approach, suitable for overdispersed count data.

Methods: A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 263 medical and pharmacy students at the Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad. A structured questionnaire assessed students' knowledge, self-assessed proficiency, and attitudes regarding probiotics. Predictors of knowledge scores included gender, study year, chronic disease status, course attendance, lifestyle, and self-evaluated knowledge. The NBR model was applied due to observed overdispersion in the count data, with model fit evaluated using deviance, Pearson Chi-square, and the Omnibus test.

Results: The NBR model showed good fit (deviance/df = 1.176; Pearson/df = 1.043; Omnibus $\chi^2 = 107.964$, $p < 0.001$). Study year and self-assessed knowledge were significant predictors. Each additional study year increased knowledge scores by 22.4% (IRR = 1.224), while each point of self-rated knowledge increased scores by 13.4% (IRR = 1.134). Other variables were not significant.

Conclusion: This study demonstrates the utility of NBR for identifying key predictors of knowledge in educational research. Advanced study level and higher self-perception of knowledge significantly correlated with better knowledge, underscoring the need for targeted educational interventions early in the medical curriculum.

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